

CRYSTALLIZATION AND PROPERTIES OF SOL-GEL DERIVED BAS (BARIUM ALUMINOSILICATE) GLASS-CERAMIC

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ABSTRACT

The crystallization of BAS gel glasses via a sol-gel process was investigated. The formation mechanism of a uniform and fine grain microstructure in BAS glass-ceramics without adding nucleating agent was studied by the analysis of non-isothermal crystallization kinetics and gel glass structure. Glass-ceramics with above 80 vol% of celsian can be obtained by adding 5wt% celsian as seeds. The relationship of microstructure and properties of hot-pressed glass-ceramics was investigated. Strengths of 204 MPa at 1250°C and 156 MPa at room temperature were obtained with a mullite-bonded celsian glass-ceramic.

INTRODUCTION

BAS glass-ceramics are potential matrix of fiber-reinforced composites for high temperature structural applications in 1200~1250°C. BAS glasses could be transformed to hexacelsian or celsian in suitable conditions. Celsian has a low thermal expansion coefficient of $2.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and is stable at below 1590°C. It is possible for celsian to get thermal match with some fibers. Hexacelsian has high thermal expansion coefficient of $8.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, is stable at above 1590°C and has a rapid inversion from hexagonal to orthorhombic phase at 300°C accompanied by a 3% volume change. Therefore, hexacelsian is not suitable as a matrix of composite. To prepare BAS glasses near $\text{BaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$ composition, the melting temperature must be as high as 2000°C. Hexacelsian crystallizes out from BAS glasses normally at above 1000°C, and the transformation from hexacelsian into celsian is very difficult. Recently, Debsikdar [1] reported that BAS glass could be synthesised by a sol-gel process, but the gel was turbid. The room temperature strength of the BAS glass-ceramic was in the range of 60~120MPa[2]. No report on the high temperature strength of the BAS glass-ceramics has been found up to now. It was the propose of this study to investigate the crystallization behavior of BAS glass via a sol-gel process, to examine the effect of adding celsian seeds on hexacelsian-celsian transition, and to understand the role of mullite in BAS glass-ceramic in improving the mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The compositions of specimens are listed in Table 1. the BAS glass—ceramic specimens were prepared by hot—pressing of gel glass powders obtained through sol—gel process.

Table 1 Composition and hot—pressing parameters of specimens

Specimen	Composition (wt %)				hot—pressing Parameters	
	BaO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Celsius Seeds	precess	pressure (MPa)
A	37	26	37	0	950°C, 0.5h+1200°C, 0.5h	
B	37	26	37	5	950°C, 0.5h+1200°C, 0.5h	7~15
C	25	37	38	5	950°C, 0.5h+1400°C, 0.5h	

Crystallization kinetics of the gel glass was studied by DTA (Du Pont Thermal Analyzst—2000). The degree of crystallinity in the specimens was examined by XRD (Ricoh D/MAX—3C Diffractometer). The microstructure of hot—pressed specimens was observed with a SEM (Hitachi S—5700) and a TEM (Hitachi H—800). The specimens were lightly etched with HF for SEM observation. The flexural strength of the specimens was measured in three—point bending test (Instron machine). The size of the specimen was $H \times W \times L = 3 \times 4 \times 40$ mm and the span was 30mm. The crosshead speed of strength test was 0.5mm/min. The elastic modulus was estimated through a three—point bending test at a crosshead speed of 0.05mm/min. The thermal expansion coefficient of specimens was measured at the heating rate of 3°C/min from 20°C to 1300°C with a High Temperature Horizontal Dilatometer made in our laboratory. The measured length of the specimen was 50mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Characterestic and behavior of crystallization of BAS gel glass.

(1) Characteretic of crystallization

The glass transition temperature (T_g), the onset temperature of crystallization (T_c), the peak maximum temperature of crystallization (T_p) and the full width of the crystallization peak at half—maximum (ΔT_{FWHM}) from DTA curve with variable heating rate were listed in Table 2. The kinetic mode proposed by Bansal [3] was used to evaluate the kinetic parameters for the non—isothermal crystallization of specimen A. the mode was expressed as:

$$\ln(T_p^2/\alpha) = \ln(E/R\nu) + E/RT_p \quad (1)$$

where, α is the heating rate. E is the activation energy. R is the gas constant and ν is the frequency factor. The plots of $\ln(T_p^2/\alpha)$ vs $1/T_p$ were shown in Fig. 1. It shows a linear relationship. According to Eqn(1), E and ν were calculated from linear least squares fitting of the

Fig. 1 Plots of $\ln(T_p^2/a)$ against reciprocal of $1000/T_p$ for the crystallization of specimen A

experimental data (see also Table 2). T_g , T_c and T_p from DTA curve and the kinetic parameters for a molten BAS glass composition is close to specimen A from [2] were also given in Table 2. Table 2 shows that, compared with the molten glass, the gel glass has a higher T_g , and lower T_c and T_p . The parameters of glass stability $[(T_c - T_g)/T_g]$ and the activation energy of the gel glass are also less. The experimental results and kinetic analysis indicate that BAS gel glass crystallize easily during densification.

Table 2 Characteristic temperature from DTA curve and kinetic parameters of specimen A

	heating rate ($^{\circ}\text{C}, \text{min}^{-1}$)	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	ΔT_{FWHM} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	n	E ($\text{KJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)	ν (sec^{-1})
gel glass	5	933	1021	1068	27	2.94		
	10	941	1032	1085	26	2.98		
	20	951	1046	1104	26	3.06	522	6.9×10^{17}
	30	957	1056	1118	23	3.14		
	40	961	1064	1125	21	3.30		
molten glass*	10	907	1058	1098			553	2.2×10^{19}

* composition; $38\text{BaO} - 27\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - 35\text{SiO}_2$

The Avrami exponents (n) of specimen A for different heating rate were calculated from the following expression derived by Augis and Bennett[4]:

$$n = \frac{2.5}{\Delta T} \cdot \frac{T_p^2}{E/R} \quad (2)$$

The results are also shown in Table 2. The average value of n is 3.08. The crystallization of specimen A proceeds in the mode of bulk crystallization. The SEM photograph (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 SEM photograph of specimen A showing uniform and fine grains

shows the uniform and fine grains ($0.5\mu\text{m}$ or less) of a BAS glass—ceramic (specimen A). The grain size of the molten BAS glass is about $10\mu\text{m}$, much coarser than that of specimen A. The large interior surface area and the large amount of residual OH groups in gel glass act as the nucleation sites, and cause the rapid nucleation and formation of the fine grain microstructure.

(2) Isothermal crystallization behavior

The isothermal crystallization behavior of specimen A examined by XRD is shown in Fig. 3. Specimen A is x-ray amorphous at below 950°C . Hexacelsian begin to crystallize at above

Fig. 3 Powder X-ray diffraction pattern of specimen A

1000°C. The hexacelsian amount increases with enhancing temperature (See Fig. 4), and the crystallization of hexacelsian is nearly complete at about 1100°C.

Fig. 4 Relationship of hexacelsian content and heat treatment temperature

2. TRANSFORMATION FROM HEXACELSIAN INTO CELSIAN

XRD quantitative analysis shows that specimen B contains more than 80 vol% celsian when heated at 1200°C for 7 hours. This indicates that the addition of celsian as seeds can accelerate the transition of hexacelsian—celsian.

3. EFFECT OF PHASE COMPONENT AND MICROSTRUCTURE ON PROPERTIES

The XRD analysis results and properties of three glass—ceramics (hot—pressing specimen) are given in Table 3. the strength of BAS glass—ceramic with hexacelsian (Specimen A) decreases severely with enhancing temperature. The strength at 1250°C is only 50% of the

Table 3 Properties of three BAS glass—ceramic specimens

specimen	crystalline phase (XRD analysis)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)				Thermal expansion coefficient (°C ⁻¹)	
			RT	1100°C	1200°C	1250°C		1300°C
A	Hexacelsian	77	138	108	99	72	65	7.4×10^{-6}
B	celsian 82 hexacelsian 18	86	134	125	118	100	90	4.2×10^{-6}
C	celsian 53 mullit 26 hexacelsian 15 corundum 6	107	156	138	208	204	180	4.8×10^{-6}

room temperature strength. The strength of BAS glass—ceramic with celsian as a main phase also decreases at 1250°C and is about 70% of the room temperature strength. The room temperature and high temperature of specimen C with a microstructure of mullite—bonded celsian (or minor hexacelsian) are the highest among the three specimens. What is more, the strength increases with enhancing temperature. The strength reaches a maximum value at 1200~1250°C. The order of elastic modulus from high to low is specimen C, B and A. The thermal expansion coefficient of specimen A is the highest among the three specimens, and those of specimen B and C are very close.

There is a small amount of glass phase in the grain boundary of specimen A as well as B from the wide grain boundary and a amorphous diffraction ring (See Fig. 5). These glass phases cause

(A) Bright-field image showing wide grain boundary

(B) Amorphous diffraction ring

Fig. 5 TEM photograph of specimen A

Fig. 6 SEM photograph of specimen C showing the bonding action of mullite

the decrease of high temperature strengths of specimen A and B. Due to the 3% volume change by the hexagonal—orthorhombic inversion, the strength of specimen A is the lowest among the three specimens. In the case of the mullite—bonded celsian (or minor heracelsian), the glass phases in the grainboundary were separated into island (See Fig. 6). The sliding motion of grains was obstructed by the bonding action of mullite at high temperatures, and the needle—like mullites also act as fibers to reinforce the matrix. Therefore, the high temperature strength of specimen C is increased to a great extent. The strengths of specimen A and B are higher than that of BAS glass—ceramic from molten glass due to the fine grain microstructure of specimen A and B. Because most hexacelsian transforms to celsian, the thermal expansion coefficients of specimen B and C are less than that of specimen A.

CONCLUSION

A uniform and fine grain microstructure in gel—derived BAS glass—ceramics without adding nucleation agent can be obtained due to the large surface and the large number of OH groups in the gel glass.

Adding celsian as seeds can promote efficiently the transition of hexacelsian to celsian. When adding 5wt% celsian into BAS gel glass, above 80% celsian in BAS glass—ceramic was obtained through a heat treatment at 1200°C for 7 hours.

The BAS glass—ceramic with celsian (or minor hexacelsian) bonded by mullite has the highest room temperature and high temperature strength among the three specimens, while the thermal expansion coefficient is close to that of the BAS glass—ceramic with 80 vol% or more celsian. Therefore, BAS glass—ceramic with mullite—bonded celsian is potentially an excellent matrix of composite to use at about 1250°C.

REFERENCE

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